

Influence of information literacy skills on postgraduate students' use of electronic information resources in public university libraries, North geopolitical zone, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of information literacy skills (ILS) on postgraduate (PG) students' use of electronic information resources (EIRs) with a view to ascertaining the relationship between ILS and use of EIRs of public university libraries in North geopolitical zone, Nigeria. The study adopted quantitative research approach using cross sectional survey research design. The population of the study was 1416 library registered PG students. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 425 PG students as sample size for the study. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that a weak, positive but significant relationship exist between postgraduate students' level of ILS and use of EIRs. The findings also revealed that there was a positive, multiple relationships between information identification skills, strategic skills, evaluation skills, information use skills and use of EIRs. The paper has provided valuable insight on the relationship between ILS and use of EIRs. This would form the bases for making appropriate decisions to guide policy and practice with regards to ILS acquisition and effective use of EIRs. The study concludes that in order to effectively use EIRs, PG students must possess high level of ILS. This would assist them in having access to current, authentic, relevant and up to date information. The study, therefore, recommended that university libraries should sustain the provision of EIRs and also organize training workshops to expose PG students to more practical aspects of ILS and use of EIRs. This paper is an empirical research that contributes to the existing body of knowledge.

Keywords: Information Literacy Skills, Electronic Information Resources, Postgraduate Students, Public University, Nigeria

Introduction

Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) are information resources that can be accessed and used via Information and Communication Technology (ICTs) devices. The resources facilitate quick access to and use of information by multiple users. According to Thanuskodi, (2012) ERs are electronic representation of information available in various forms such as e-books, e-journals, digital libraries, e-magazines, full text databases, image collections, e-periodicals, CD-ROMs. However, it is not the availability of the resources that matters rather, the skills in using the

resources. To this regards, in order to effectively use EIRs, possession of information literacy skills is vital. The concept of Information Literacy (IL) emphasizes skills to identify, search, locate and evaluate information. This presupposes that IL seems to consist of a number of interrelated abilities connected to effective use of information.

Skyline College (2021) defined Information Literacy Skills (ILS) as a set of abilities that enable individuals to find, evaluate, use and communicate information in various formats. Julien and Boon (2004) emphasized that information literate individuals should possess specific online searching skills, which include the ability to select appropriate search terminology and construct a logical strategy. In view of this, successful search may depend on one's level of information search skills. In addition, students should also be able to evaluate EIRs by ascertaining their relevance, credibility, reliability and authenticity. Furthermore, possession of information use skills is also vital as it gives value to students' research work. It also prevents them from copy and paste which characterized students' use of information. Odede and Zewedde (2018) concluded that ILS has overbearing influence on the extent to which PG students can use EIRs. In effect, therefore, testing hypotheses to determine relationships in order to substantiate these claims or prove it otherwise becomes vital. It is on this basis that this study investigated the influence of information literacy skills on PG students' use of EIRs in public university libraries in north geopolitical zone, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) have the potential to enhance convenient access to and use of information by multiple user. The resources may be used for a variety of personal, social, professional as well as for academic and research purposes. Echem and Wokoma (2022) opined that EIRs offer the 21st century students new opportunities that were not available to previous generations; yet, their potential remain untapped by students who struggle to navigate and sift through massive EIRs.

Preliminary observations and existing literature suggest that PG students frequently underutilize EIRs for their studies. This points to a poor information literacy skills to effectively identify, search, critically evaluate and use EIRs, which leaves students ill-equipped to effectively manage information overload. Consequently, students will not be able to manage information overload, there will be poor academic performance as well as missed research opportunities. The information age demands sophisticated skills for navigating vast electronic information resources. This makes one to wonder and ask several questions; could this be as a result of lack ILS; what then, is the relationship between ILS and use of EIRs.

It is against this that this study focused on determining the relationship between ILS of PG students and use of EIRs of public universities in north geopolitical zone, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. Is there any relationship between Postgraduate (PG) students' level of information identification skills and use of Electronic Information Resources (EIRs) in public universities, North Geopolitical Zones, Nigeria?
2. Is there any relationship between PG students' level of strategic skills and use of EIRs in the universities studied?
3. Is there any relationship between PG students' level of information evaluation skills and use of EIRs in the universities studied?
4. Is there any relationship between PG students' level of information use skills and use EIRs in the universities studied?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested in the study:

- Ho₁ There is no significant relationship between the level of information Identification skills of PG students and use of electronic information resources.
- Ho₂ There is no significant relationship between the level of strategic skills of PG students and use of electronic information resources.
- Ho₃ There is no significant relationship between the level of information evaluation skills of PG students and use of electronic information resources.
- Ho₄ There is no significant relationship between the level of information use skills of PG students and use of electronic information resources.

Review of Related Literature

Several studies have been conducted all over the world on ILS and use of EIRs. For example,

Adeniran and Onuoha (2018) investigated the influence of ILS on PG students' use of EIRs in private universities in southwest Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design with 2805 PG students as population of which 550 were sampled for the study. The findings revealed that there was a significant positive correlation between the two variables. This study was conducted in southwest Nigeria and in private universities. Private universities have different funding body compared to public universities. In view of this, there is need for similar study in public universities in northern Nigeria.

In a related study, Ugwulebo and Okuonghae (2021) investigated the relationship that exists between ILS and utilization of EIRs by PG students in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. The population of the study was 3744 while the sample size was 374 determined using Taro Yamane's 1969 method for sampling. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data

collection. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings of the study revealed that a significant relationship exist among PG students' knowledge of electronic resources, search skills, access to information, information evaluation capability and their utilization of EIRs. The study concluded that it is imperative for information literacy programs to be included in the curriculum of students across all levels of study.

Uwhejevwe, (2022) investigated information retrieval skills and utilization of electronic resources for enhanced research by PG students of Ignatius Ajuru university of education library, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised all library registered PG students. Accidental sampling techniques was used to sample only 34 PG students. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using PPMC. Findings revealed that ILS, system operational skills and strategic search skills, correlated significantly with PG students' utilization of electronic resources. The relationship between the variables was weak due to lack of knowledge of the three skills; hence, PG students do not adequately use electronic resources to retrieve information for research work. This study is a case study, which findings cannot be generalized to larger settings.

Alegbeleye, Ikonne and Ladele, (2023) conducted a study on ILS and use of library resources by undergraduates in universities in Ogun state, Nigeria Using survey research design, with 15,400 undergraduate students as population for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 390 students as respondents. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that ILS had positive significant influence on use of library resources by the final year students. The study concluded t2024ILS promoted use of library resources. The study recommended that library management should introduce students to practical training in the Use of library resources. In addition, library resources and qualified staff should be provided to increase the interest and abilities of undergraduates to use the library resources.

Yusuf, (2024) examined the proficiency of PG students as correlates of EIRs usage for research in universities in northwest Nigeria. The population of the study was 26,531 PG students from 12 universities. The study adopted descriptive correlational design. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 530 PG students as sample size for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Only 499 questionnaire were returned and found usable out of the 530 distributed. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that the proficiency of the respondents in using EIRs was high, however, the extent of use of the resources was low. Findings from the hypothesis revealed a significant relationship between the respondents' proficiency level and use of EIRs.

Theoretical Framework

Several information literacy models have been developed across the world. However, this study adapted the Seven Pillars model by the Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL, 1999) and the Big6 model by Eisenberg and Berkowitz (1999).

Seven Pillars Information Literacy Model

The first model adapted, which is the Seven Pillars IL Model, is a model of information skills in higher education developed as a result of the Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL) Advisory Committee on Information Literacy at United Kingdom in the year 1999. The name of the model is seven pillars information literacy model. It is an information problem-solving model, which presents five areas of expertise including novice to expert. The components of the model states that an information literate individual should possess: the ability to recognize a need for information, the ability to distinguish ways in which gap may be addressed, the ability to construct strategies for locating information, the ability to locate and access information, the ability to compare and evaluate information obtained from different sources, (SCONUL, 1999). This study adapted this model. The justification for this was based on the fact that the model has comprehensive logical set of skills that can be used to address the needs of this study. In addition, the model has been applied as theoretical framework in several studies; such as the works of (Mckinney and Sen (2012); (Al-Issa, 2013) (Annunobi and Udem, 2015); (Issa, Amusa, Olarongbe, Igwe and Oguntayo, 2015); and (Gowri and Padma, 2018).

Seven Pillars Model is flexible. The model serve as guideline for developing information skills. However, despite the strength of the model, there are still few drawbacks. Onoriode and Basil (2016) stated that information use is the factor that drives all other forms of information behavior, since it represents the ultimate purpose for which information resources are needed and sought. However, this crucial skill was not explicitly captured in seven pillars model. Accordingly, this study considers it appropriate to include the Big6 IL model as the second model guiding this study.

The Big6 Model of Information Literacy

Michael Eisenberg and Bob Berkowitz of United States of America developed the Big6 skills model in the year 1990 as a problem solving strategy to access and use information. The model emphasizes that successful information problem solving encompasses six steps strategy with sub-steps. (Eisenberg and Berkowitz 2004). The components of the model as cited in Ojedokun, 2011 include: Task definition, information seeking strategy, location and access, use of information, synthesis and evaluation. The model has been widely applied as theoretical framework in several studies; such as the studies of (Murray, 2011) and (Adeniran and Onuoha, 2018). They emphasized that the Big6 information skills model is more encompassing in terms of information access and utilization. This study adapted The Big6 model. The justification for this was based on the fact that the model emphasized the use of information. It also stands out to identify the skills an individual is expected to possess in order to use information. However, the model does not emphasize information technology skills as a core part of being information literate. The model also relied on problem solving rhetoric and users of information usually lack well-informed statements of information needs (Mitchell, nd).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study explains that PG students who possess the ability to identify, construct search strategy to search/locate, evaluate and use information will be able to effectively use electronic information resources. Figure 1 depicts the conceptual framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for the relationship between ILS and Use of EIRs

The proposed conceptual framework consists of three components. The first component consists of the theoretical environment; the second component is the conceptual environment while the third component is the outcome. The theoretical foundation was framed on the two models used in the study; that is SCONUL Seven Pillars (1999) and the Big6 by Eisenberg and Berkowitz (1990). It is the theoretical base upon which the major variables of the study were framed. The base integrated some vital constructs of Seven Pillars model and the Big6 model to describe the skills an individual is expected to possess in order to become information literate.

The second component of the proposed conceptual framework depicts the conceptual environment, which projected the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study as depicted in the conceptual framework.

Information Identification skills: this was conceptualized as PG students’ ability to identify why they need information and also understand what type of information resources would be needed to answer their questions.

Strategic Skills: this was conceptualized as PG students' ability to search, locate and access EIRs. PG students should be able to use several search techniques to produce best search result. They should also be able to use location and access tools to find out where EIRs are located. Once the resources are located, what needs to be done is to evaluate the resources.

Information Evaluation Skills: this was conceptualized as PG students' ability to appraise EIRs to determine which information is authentic, relevant and reliable. Once PG students are able to identify, search, locate, access and evaluate EIRs, the next stage is to be able to use the information effectively.

Information Use Skills: this was conceptualized as PG students' ability to observe copyright laws by avoiding plagiarism, competently paraphrase sources of information as well as cite and acknowledge people's work using appropriate reference styles.

Effective Use of EIRs: The third component of the proposed conceptual framework exhibits the outcome. It explains that PG students would be able to use EIRs when they possess ILS.

Methodology

Quantitative research methodology was adopted for this study, using cross-sectional survey research design. The population of the study was 1416 library registered PG students. The study adopted stratified random sampling technique. A sampling frame of 30% was used, which yielded 425 PG students as sample size of the study. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. The instrument was administered by the researcher and two other trained research assistants. Only 387(91%) copies of the questionnaire were returned and found usable despite several replacements and follow up. The data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis in order to find out whether a significant relationship exist between the independent variables and the dependent variable of the study.

Findings of the Study

1.1 There is no significant relationship between level of Information Identification Skills (IIS) and use of EIRs. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficient was computed to identify the relationship between the two variables. The analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

PPMC of the Relationship between the Level of IIS and Use of EIRs

Variables	N	M	SD	r	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Information Identification Skills	387	3.92	.90	.278*	0.000*	Significant	Reject Ho
Use of Electronic EIRs	387	3.67	.96				

Note: N: Number of respondents, SD: Standard Deviation, r: Correlation Coefficient, Sig: Significant.

**Correlation is Significant at 0.05 Level (2-tailed) SPSS Version 22. R=. 278*, p<. 05

The analysis in Table 1 reveals that correlation is significant at 0.05 level of confidence and the relationship is positive, weak and significant with coefficient r = .278 and p< .05. This implies that as the respondents' level of IIS increases, their use of EIRs also increases, which indicates a direct relationship between the two variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted, which implies that there is significant relationship between the level of IIS of the respondents and use of EIRs.

1.2 There is no significant relationship between level of Strategic Skills (SS) and Use of EIRs.

PPMC coefficient was also used to test hypothesis two. The analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

PPMC of the Relationship between the Level of SS and Use of EIRs

Variables	N	M	SD	r	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Strategic Skills (SS)	387	3.82	.99	0.313*	0.000*	Significant	Reject Ho
Use of EIRs	387	3.67	.96				

Note: N: Number of respondents, SD: Standard Deviation, r: Correlation Coefficient, Sig: Significant.

**Correlation is Significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed). R=. 313, p<. 05

Findings in Table 2 revealed that there is a relationship between SS and use of EIRs. It showed the coefficient (r) = .313 and p< .05), which indicates that the relationship is weak, positive and significant. It thus implies that as SS of the respondents improve their use of EIRs also increases. This also indicates a direct positive relationship between the two variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis two is also rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted, which implies that there is significant relationship between the level of SS of PG students and use of EIRS.

1.3 There is no significant relationship between the level of Information Evaluation Skills (IES) and use of EIRs. PPMC coefficient was also used to test hypothesis three. The analysis result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3

PPMC of the Relationship between the Level of IES and Use of EIRS

Variables	N	M	SD	r	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Information Evaluation Skills	387	3.77	.95	0.351*	0.000*	Significant	Reject Ho
Use of EIRS	387	3.67	.96				

Note: N: Number of respondents, SD: Standard Deviation, r: Correlation Coefficient, Sig: Significant.

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed). R=0.351, p<.05

In Table 3, analysis indicated that IES of the respondents also have weak, positive and significant relationship with use of EIRS, (r = .351 and p< .05). This means that as the respondents' IES improve, use of EIRS also improves. Hence, null hypothesis 3 is also rejected while alternate is accepted, which suggests that there is significant positive relationship between the level of IES of the respondents and use of EIRS.

1.4 There is no significant relationship between level of Information Use Skills and use of EIRs. PPMC coefficient was also used to test hypothesis four. Table 4 presents.

Table 4

PPMC of the Relationship between the Level of IUS and Use of EIRS

Variables	N	M	SD	r	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Information Evaluation Skills	387	3.90	.94	0.369*	0.000*	Significant	Reject Ho
Use of EIRS	387	3.67	.96				

Note: N: Number of respondents, SD: Standard Deviation, r: Correlation Coefficient, Sig: Significant.

**Correlation is significant at 0.005 level (2-tailed). R=.369, p<.05

In Table 4, findings revealed that IUS of the respondents have a weak, positive and significant relationship with use of ERS as the coefficient (r) = .369 and p< .05). Thus, it can be inferred that when PG students' ability to use EIRS improves, use of EIRS also increases. Hence, null hypothesis four is also rejected while the alternate is accepted, which implies that there is significant positive relationship between the level of IUS of the respondents and use of EIRS.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings with regards to hypotheses 1-4 revealed that there is weak positive and significant relationship between the four constructs of ILS (IIS, SS, IES, IUS) and use of EIRs. Therefore, the four hypotheses were rejected, hence, there is significant relationship between the four constructs of ILS and respondents' use of EIRs. Based on the result, it can be inferred that when the level of ILS of PG students rises, use of EIRs increases. These findings are in line with that of Uwhejevwe (2022) which stated that ILS, system operational skills and strategic search skills had weak but

significant relationship with respondents' use of EIRs. In the same vein, the findings in the present study is in support of Umeji, Efe and Lucky, (2013) study where their analysis revealed that there was significant, direct positive relationship between ILS and use of EIRs. The result of this survey also aligned with that of Okon, Etuk and Akpan, (2014) whose study concluded that there was a significant relationship between ILS and information use by students in two south university libraries in Nigeria. The findings also corroborated the work of Adeniran and Onuoha (2018) that there was significant correlation between ILS and use of e-resources. It is worthy to note that the present study confirms that as the level of ILS of PG students increase, use of ERs also increases. This is a pointer to the fact that possession of ILS is very vital for effective use of EIRs. PG students may require more exposure to IL initiatives in order to become experts in maximizing the potentials of EIRs.

Based on the findings of the study, the gaps established from previous studies and literature, it has been established that PG students have attained certain level IL skills for using EIRs. This means that the PG students are likely to have a working knowledge of different learning resources that will complement their studies, and be able to:

1. Independently select the most appropriate resources for a specific task
2. Keep up-to-date with any changes to the resources selected for that task
3. Independently carry out a wide-ranging, systematic literature search (and be confident that the information found represents a thorough sample of the literature)
4. Filter and critically evaluate information obtained from any source to ascertain its quality and relevance to the purpose at hand (e.g. determine any bias in approach, the validity of its outcomes, etc.
5. Accurately and appropriately refer to and reference the thoughts, ideas and work of others (including published authors, other students, anonymous websites, etc.).

However, with proliferation of digital resources, PG students are expected to have a reasonable idea of how to find, retrieve and work with different sources of information, but the key thing here is to ensure that they know how to do this as effectively as possible. Drawing on the themes evident from the findings of this study, the existing literature on IL and bearing in mind the weaknesses of the existing models, the researcher proposed a framework for Digital Information Literacy (DIL) programme. This would serve as a new model that can help PG students to recognize how their DIL skills are progressing during their information searching and use and how their DIL skills relate to their academic, personal and professional needs.

The framework is based around five core skills that cover:

1. Understanding and engaging in digital practices
2. Finding information
3. Critically evaluating information, online interactions and online tools
4. Managing and communicating information

5. Collaborating and sharing digital content.

Theoretical Implication: Specifically, this study has contributed to the frontier of knowledge with regard to the state of the art on the relationship between the level of ILS and use of EIRs. The integration of the findings of this study to the weaknesses of the existing models of IL produced a new framework for the new model: Digital IL Programme for PG students. This position would provide valuable insight and areas of IL for librarians and faculty members to constantly work on when advancing the IL level of PG students.

Practical Implication: The university/library management, the department of library and information sciences could use the proposed framework for the overall design of practical aspects of ILS; influencing provision of dedicated IL policy, realistic curriculum and workable syllabus that integrates courses on digital IL in all PG programmes. Consequently, strong synergy between the library and the faculty would be maintained. This would further foster collaboration between librarians and faculty members in the universities in teaching IL to PG students. The libraries and the faculty members on this important issue could also practice collaborative researches. When university management provide information infrastructure and librarians collaborate with faculty members in teaching IL, PG students would become more information literate to effectively use EIRs.

Summary of the Findings

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

1. There is weak, positive and significant relationship between levels of information needs skills and use of EIRs among the PG students.
2. There is weak, positive and significant relationship between level of strategic skills and use of EIRs among the PG students.
3. There is weak, positive and significant relationship between level of information evaluation skills and use of EIRs among the PG students.
4. There is weak, positive and significant relationship between level of information use skills and use of EIRs among the PG students.

Conclusion

We are living in an era, where our daily activities are very much dependent on information to solve problems and fulfill tasks. To this regards, possession of ILS becomes an integral aspect of successful higher education studies. The study showed a significant relationship between ILS and use of EIRs. The study, therefore, concludes that effective use of EIRs among PG students of public universities in North geopolitical zone, Nigeria could be met through possession of information identification skills, strategic skills, evaluation skills as well as information use skills. These skills are needed to face the 21st century technological world.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were provided as follows:

1. University libraries should sustain the provision of EIRs and create more awareness to the university community in order to raise the level of use of the resources.
2. PG students should be exposed to intermittent assignments, built around research situations. This will motivate them to have access to EIRs that would link them up with any part of the world, thereby enhancing use of the resources as well as their ILS.
3. Information literacy programmes should be incorporated into PG curricula.
4. Information literacy training and workshops should be organized on a regular bases in order to expose students to more practical aspects of ILS and use of EIRs.

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